

Structural behavior of silver sulfide under strong compression

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Abstract

Angle-dispersive X-ray diffraction measurements have been performed in acanthite, Ag_2S , up to 18 GPa in order to investigate the high-pressure structural behavior of this compound. They have been complemented by *ab initio* electronic structure calculations. From our experimental data, we have determined that two different high-pressure phase transitions take place at 5 and 10.5 GPa. The first pressure-induced transition is from the initial anti- PbCl_2 -type monoclinic structure (S.G. $P2_1/n$) to an orthorhombic Ag_2Se -type structure (S.G. $P2_12_12_1$), which is a strong distortion of the initial phase. The compression of the lattice parameters and the equation of state of both phases have been determined. A second phase transition to a $P2_1/n$ phase has been found, which results to be a slight modification of the low-pressure structure. The initial monoclinic phase was fully recovered after decompression, the intermediate orthorhombic HP1 structure not being observed during the down-stroke. *Ab initio* calculations confirm the experimental high-pressure sequence. Standard density functional theory (DFT) presents some deficiencies for modelling the electronic structure of the initial monoclinic phase that can be overcome using a GGA+U methodology. Good agreement with the experimental values is found for the cell parameters, their evolution with pressure and transition pressures. Finally, the atomic arrangement in silver sulphide is discussed in relation to the structural behaviour of other binary sulfides and the cation subarray of the corresponding oxides, Ag_2SO_3 and Ag_2SO_4 .

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1. Introduction

In the last thirty years there has been a rapid development of experiments and theory in high-pressure (HP) condensed-matter physics. The diamond-anvil cell technique, for instance, has made possible to characterize *in situ* a vast number of high-pressure phases of different chemical systems¹. However, in spite of all the new progresses, our knowledge of the structural behaviour of matter under extreme conditions remains very poor. The ultimate reasons why pressure-induced phase transitions take place are still not well understood. In order to deeper understand the performance of atoms at these conditions and to find the existing systematic trends, accurate structural studies of isostoichiometric chemical-related compounds are therefore needed.

In particular, alkaline-metal sulfides, M_2S , form a family of compounds that has recently been of renewed interest regarding their HP phases²⁻⁷. The completion of HP X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements on the group IA sulfides up to 20 GPa evidenced the existence of a common trend in their pressure-induced transformations. Thus, pressure drives structural changes from the anti-fluorite-type through the anti-cotunnite-type to the Ni_2In -type structures and the phase stability of these sulfides seems to depend on both, the pressure and the ionic radii ratio⁴. This common trend should be, however, validated for other binary sulfides, like those of group IB metals for instance. As early as 1869, Dmitri Mendeleev arranged the elements according their chemical properties and placed copper (Cu), silver (Ag) and gold (Au) in the same column as alkaline metals. These similar properties are related to the configuration of the outer electron shell, with only one valence electron. Nevertheless, these elements present a distinguishing feature compared to alkaline metals: their electronegativity is considerably larger. Due to this fact, the group IB sulfides: Cu_2S , Ag_2S and Au_2S , may be considered as formed by “covalent” bonds, instead of the “ionic” bonds existing in the alkaline-metal sulfides.

One of the members of this family of compounds is acanthite, the stable form of silver sulfide Ag_2S at ambient conditions⁸, which crystallizes in the monoclinic system, space group $P2_1/n$. It adopts an anti-cotunnite structure (anti- $PbCl_2$), like Cs_2S at the

same conditions. Two other polymorphs of silver sulfide are known: (i) Upon heating above 176 °C, there is a phase conversion to a body-centered cubic form (S.G. *Im-3m*) referred to as argentite^{9, 10}. In this phase, the silver atoms are randomly distributed over the interstitial sites of a bcc sulphur lattice, reason why this HT phase has been considered as a possible ionic superconductor¹¹ and, (ii) Further heating above 586 °C results in the conversion to a face-centered cubic polymorph. However, the reliability of the existing powder diffraction studies on this latter high-temperature polymorph has recently been questioned¹².

The aim of this work is to study experimentally the structural stability of this compound under pressure in order to compare its behaviour with that observed in alkaline-metal sulfides (i.e. check if it follows the same structural sequence empirically observed in these compounds) and try to understand the existing differences. Room-temperature angle-dispersive X-ray diffraction (ADXRD) measurements were carried out up to 18 GPa using a diamond-anvil cell (DAC). The diffraction experiments allow us to characterize two high-pressure phases, the transitions taking place at 5 GPa and 10.5 GPa. The experimental measurements have been complemented with *ab initio* total-energy calculations that support the experimental results.

2. Experimental and theoretical methods

2.1 Experimental details

To perform X-ray powder diffraction measurements, commercial silver sulfide powder with 99.99% purity (Alfa Aesar, Prod. Nr. 12113) was crushed in a mortar with a pestle to obtain a micron-sized powder. Ambient conditions X-ray diffraction confirmed that our sample has an anticotunnite-type structure.

Two independent high-pressure angle-dispersive X-ray diffraction experiments were conducted at room temperature. Experiment 1 was carried out up to 18 GPa with a Xcalibur diffractometer (Oxford Diffraction Ltd.). X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained on a 135-mm Atlas CCD detector placed at 110 mm from the sample using $K_{\alpha 1}:K_{\alpha 2}$ molybdenum radiation (0.7093 and 0.7136 Å, respectively). The X-ray beam was collimated to a diameter of 300 μm. The same set-up was used previously to successfully characterize the high-pressure phases of other sulfides and oxides in the same pressure range^{3, 4, 13}. Measurements were performed in a modified Merrill-Bassett

diamond-anvil cell (DAC) with diamond culets of 450 μm . The diamond cell used for these experiments allows access to an angular range $4\theta = 50^\circ$. The Ag_2S black powder was loaded in a 160 μm -diameter hole of the stainless-steel gasket preindented to thickness of about 50 μm . A 4:1 methanol:ethanol mixture was used as pressure-transmitting medium. Exposure times were typically of 1 hour. The CrysAlis software, version 171.34.49 (Oxford Diffraction Ltd.) was used for data collection and preliminary data reduction.

Experiment 2, up to 17 GPa, was performed at the I15 beamline of the Diamond Light Source with an incident monochromatic wavelength of 0.4246 \AA . The DAC and the sample loading were similar to those of experiment 1, with the exception of the pressure-transmitting medium used: a mixture 16:3:1 methanol:ethanol:water. The monochromatic X-ray beam was focused down to $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ using Kickpatrick-Baez mirrors. A pinhole placed before the sample position was used as a cleanup aperture for filtering out the tail of the X-ray beam. The images were collected using a MAR345 image plate located 350 mm from the sample. Exposure times were typically of 120 seconds. Preliminary data reduction was done using the Fit2D software¹⁴.

Ruby chips evenly distributed in the pressure chamber were used to measure the pressure in both experiments by the ruby fluorescence method¹⁵. Pressures measured in different ruby chips are within 0.1 GPa below 11 GPa and within 0.2 GPa at the maximum pressure of the experiments. The observed intensities were integrated as a function of 2θ in order to give conventional, one-dimensional diffraction profiles. The indexing and refinement of the powder diffraction patterns were performed using the FULLPROF¹⁶ and POWDERCELL¹⁷ program packages. It is important to remark that, in experiment 1, the high-pressure XRD powder patterns are only considered below $2\theta = 18.3^\circ$ in the refinement process because of the appearance of the stainless-steel peaks of the gasket.

2.2 Calculation details

First-principles total-energy calculations were carried out within the DFT formalism with a plane-wave pseudopotential approach, as implemented in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP)¹⁸. We used the projector augmented wave (PAW) all-electron description of the electron-ion-core interaction¹⁹. Brillouin-zone integrals were approximated using the method of Monkhorst and Pack,²⁰ and the energies

converged with respect to the k -point density (12x8x8 and 8x12x8 meshes for the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ and orthorhombic $P2_12_12_1$ structures, respectively) and the plane-wave cutoff (420 eV). Initially, we used a conventional DFT exchange-correlation functional, within the generalized gradient approximation, the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functional (PBE)²¹. For comparison, the exchange-correlation interaction was also treated with other GGA functionals (AM05²², PBEsol²³) and under the local density approximation (LDA) in the standard parametrization of Perdew and Zunger²⁴.

To overcome the failure of DFT to describe the strongly correlated “d” electrons of Ag, the rotationally invariant form of DFT+U²⁵ was employed, with four values for $U_{\text{eff}} = U - J$ (namely 4, 5, 6, and 7 eV). Also, we accounted for the non-local correlation energies by employing the DFT+D2 methodology²⁶.

All structural relaxations were performed via a conjugate-gradient minimization of the total energy using the tetrahedron method with Blochl corrections²⁷. We note that the calculated $H(p)$ curves correspond to the static approximation (zero temperature and neglecting zero point vibrational contributions)²⁸.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Experimental structural study of Ag₂S

Figures 1a and 1b show the ADXRD data for Ag₂S at several selected pressures in the two different runs. At ambient conditions, the X-ray diffraction pattern corresponds to the monoclinic anticotunnite-type structure previously reported (S.G. $P2_1/n$, No. 14)⁸ with similar lattice parameters: $a = 4.2245(3)$ Å, $b = 6.9226(4)$, $c = 7.8631(6)$ Å and $\beta = 99.628(4)$ [$V = 226.71(2)$ Å³]. This anti-PbCl₂-type structure is very common among the alkaline-metal chalcogenides (both, at room and high-pressure) and consists of trigonal prisms of Ag atoms connected by common edges forming chains which run parallel to the ab plane (see Fig. 2a). The S atoms are located in the center of such prisms. Adjacent chains of prisms are shifted $1/2a$ along this axis (see Fig. 2b). A more detailed analysis of this structure type can be found in Ref. [2-4, 6, 7].

Under compression, the typical peak broadening of DAC experiments is observed in the XRD patterns. High-pressure X-ray diffraction patterns could be indexed in the initial monoclinic phase up to 4.7 GPa. For instance, the XRD pattern at 3.2 GPa (experiment 2) could be indexed in a monoclinic cell and, subsequently, the structural

anti-PbCl₂ model was refined by the Rietveld method (see Fig. 3). The atomic coordinates of this structure are collected in Table I. The obtained evolution for the unit-cell volume and lattice parameters of the low-pressure (LP) phase of Ag₂S are shown in Fig.4 and 5a, respectively. There, it can be seen that the contraction of the lattice parameters is rather anisotropic. For instance, according to our experiments, the relative contractions for a , b , and c between room pressure and 4.7 GPa are 2.87, 4.05, and 0.57%, respectively. As regards the values of the β angle, its variation is negligible up to 3.5 GPa and then the angle starts to decrease considerably with pressure (see Fig. 5a). A third-order Birch-Murnaghan equation of state (EOS) was used to fit our pressure-volume data. By fixing the zero-pressure volume (V_0) to its measured value, we obtained the bulk modulus, $B_0 = 38(2)$ GPa and its pressure derivative, $B'_0 = 12(2)$.

3.2 First pressure-driven phase transition

Upon further compression additional diffraction peaks appear and, in the case of the experiment 1, the peaks of the low pressure phase almost disappear completely at 5.4 GPa (see Fig. 1a). This clearly indicates the existence of a structural phase transition at this pressure. At 6.9 GPa, the new diffraction peaks could be indexed in an orthorhombic cell with lattice constants: $a = 6.7249(12)$ Å, $b = 4.1479(12)$ Å, and $c = 7.2945(11)$ Å ($V = 203.4(2)$ Å³). Therefore, this structure implies a volume change of about 1.3 % at the transition. The systematic absences in the indexed lattice planes are consistent with symmetry elements (screw axes) of the S.G. $P2_12_12_1$. This space group is also adopted by the mineral naumannite, Ag₂Se, at ambient conditions²⁹⁻³¹. Therefore, we used the structural model of silver selenide to refine by the Rietveld method the X-ray diffraction patterns above 5.4 GPa, leading to the lattice constants and atomic parameters collected in Table I (XRD pattern at 6.9 GPa). This X-ray diffraction pattern is shown in Fig. 6 together with the calculated and difference profiles to illustrate the quality of the refinement. The refined parameters were: the overall scale factor, the cell parameters, the pseudo-Voigt profile function with terms to account for the reflection anisotropic broadening and the fractional atomic coordinates. The background was manually subtracted and not refined. During the refinement process, displacement factors were physically meaningless and, for this reason, the overall displacement parameter was fixed to 0.1 Å². This high-pressure phase will be henceforth referred to as HP1 phase.

This HP1 structure, depicted in Fig. 2c, is basically a strong distortion of the initial anticotunnite phase. It can be described in a similar way as composed of chains of trigonal prisms formed by Ag atoms connected by common edges, each of these prisms being centred by a S atom. Adjacent chains of prisms are shifted approximately $1/2b$ along this axis. However, in this case, these chains are not running parallel to each other anymore. The lattice transformation has entailed a small displacement of the atoms in such a way that the chains of trigonal prisms are tilted with respect the adjacent ones (see Fig. 2d). However, the coordination number of the atoms does not change at the phase transition. The rectangular faces of the $[Ag_6]$ prisms are capped by three additional Ag atoms belonging to adjacent chains so that the coordination number of the S atoms remains 9. As regards the Ag atoms, there are two crystallographically independent Ag atoms in the orthorhombic unit cell. One Ag atom (Ag2) is surrounded by four Se atoms in a distorted tetrahedral coordination (distances ranging from 2.25 to 3.13 Å), while the second Ag atom (Ag1) exhibits a fivefold coordination defined by four Se atoms forming a rectangular face, and another Se atom that completes the square pyramid (distances ranging from 2.6 to 3.16 Å).

A different behaviour is observed in the experiment carried out with synchrotron radiation. In experiment 2, the initial monoclinic $P2_1/n$ phase coexists with the $P2_12_12_1$ orthorhombic one from 5 GPa up to 10.5 GPa (see Fig. 1b). It is important to remember here that the single difference between both experiments is the pressure medium used. Unlike the experiment 1, in experiment 2 we use a mixture 16:3:1 methanol:ethanol:water. However, this distinguishing feature should not affect to the behaviour of our compound under pressures below 10 GPa, where both pressure media are quasi-hydrostatic. We have not found yet any satisfactory explanation for such a different behaviour. One possibility could be that, as the energy of both phases is very similar in the pressure range from 5 to 10 GPa (see the Section 3.4 devoted to first-principles calculations), a slight change in loading parameters could drive the transition to occurs completely or not. In this sense, the ratio between the amount of sample and pressure medium loaded could be crucial. In any case, the quality of the XRD patterns allows us to obtain the values of the lattice constants of the HP1 structure in the pressure range 5 - 10 GPa (Fig. 5b).

The equation of state and the pressure evolution of the lattice parameters of the HP1-Ag₂S phase are shown in Fig. 4 and 5b, respectively. It can be seen that, in this HP1 phase, the *c* axis is the most compressible of the lattice constants and the *b* axis is

almost incompressible. The linear compressibility of the different axes is: $K_a = 0.015(2)$ GPa⁻¹, $K_b = 0.0002(18)$ GPa⁻¹ and $K_c = 0.0409(19)$ GPa⁻¹, which show the anisotropic compression of the orthorhombic unit cell. This anisotropy is due to the arrangement of the [Ag₆S] trigonal prisms and, in particular, is related to their relative tilting which makes these polyhedral units rather incompressible along the *b* direction. The variation of the unit cell volumes of the HP1 phase of Ag₂S with pressure could be fitted to a third-order Birch-Murnaghan equation of state, where the values of the bulk modulus (B_0) and cell volume at zero pressure (V_0) are left to vary freely and the first derivative with pressure B'_0 is fixed to 5.2 (to be better compared with theoretical results collected in Section 3.4). The obtained characteristic parameters for the $P2_12_12_1$ phase are $V_0 = 217.2(2)$ Å³ and $B_0 = 82(2)$ GPa.

3.3 Second pressure-driven phase transition

This HP1 phase is stable up to 10.5 GPa, where another transition takes place. At this point, the HP2 phase starts to appear (onset of the phase transition) and the peaks corresponding to the HP1 phase gradually loss intensity. There exists a region of coexistence of both phases between this pressure and 14 GPa, where the transition seems to be completed. The diffractograms above this pressure were of relatively poor quality, even the synchrotron data, and hindered a clear indexation of the Bragg reflections. Nevertheless, theoretical calculations come to our aid and suggested a monoclinic structure $P2_1/n$ with a β angle close to 94 degrees (see Table I and the next section, devoted to theoretical simulations) as a possible structural candidate. With this in mind, we could index the XRD pattern at 16.5 GPa on the basis of a monoclinic cell with the following lattice parameters: $a = 4.0939(12)$ Å, $b = 5.754(2)$ Å, $c = 7.9747(11)$ Å and $\beta = 93.87(2)^\circ$ ($V = 187.4(2)$ Å³). The intensities of the diffraction peaks corresponding to the structural model proposed by theoretical simulations were not far away from the experimentally observed, reason why we carried out a Rietveld refinement of the limited-quality XRD pattern at 16.5 GPa. This x-ray diffraction pattern is shown in Fig. 7 together with the calculated and difference profiles to illustrate the quality of the refinement. The refined parameters were: the overall scale factor, the cell parameters, the pseudo-Voigt profile function with terms to account for the reflection anisotropic broadening and the fractional atomic coordinates. The background was manually subtracted and not refined. Taking into consideration the

limitations of this refinement, we managed to obtain some tentative atomic coordinates for the HP2 phase. Both, the refined lattice and atomic parameters would be in excellent agreement with those previously theoretically calculated (see Table I).

This HP2 structure is represented in Fig.2e, together with the other two phases of Ag₂S. It can be seen that the HP2 phase is a subtle variation of the initial monoclinic phase, the only difference being that the bases of the trigonal prisms are now almost equilateral triangles with edges of 2.916, 2.961 and 3.061 Å and angles of 57.91°, 59.32° and 62.77° (to compare with edges of 3.13, 3.148 and 3.575 Å and angles of 55.04°, 55.53° and 69.43° at room pressure).

It is noteworthy that the initial monoclinic phase is fully recovered after decompression, the reversibility being observed in both experiments, using the 4:1 MeOH:EtOH and the 16:3:1 MeOH:EtOH:H₂O mixtures as pressure media. The lattice parameters of the recovered sample are almost identical to those of the sample prior compression: $a = 4.2274(4)$ Å, $b = 6.9246(5)$ Å, $c = 7.8688(7)$ Å and $\beta = 99.661(6)^\circ$ ($V = 227.08(4)$ Å³). Another important fact to remark is that the HP1 phase was not observed in the only downstroke XRD measurement. The sample was measured at 6.8 GPa and the powder diffractogram could be perfectly indexed into a monoclinic unit cell with constants: $a = 4.1393(11)$ Å, $b = 6.097(2)$ Å, $c = 7.9214(15)$ Å and $\beta = 96.68(2)^\circ$ ($V = 198.5(2)$ Å³). Note that these values are just in between of those of the initial room-pressure phase and the HP2 phase at 16.5 GPa, both with the same space group, $P2_1/n$. This fact supports the argument of structures being very close energetically (LP and HP1) and show the existence of a possible stepwise transformation path from the HP2 to the LP phase.

3.4 First-principles structural study of Ag₂S

Under the PBE approximation, the evolution of the calculated energy with volume for the anticotunnite-type structure (S.G.: $P2_1/n$) shows two slope changes. It reflects in a steepy behavior of the calculated cell volume and cell parameters with pressure, with steps at 12.8 and 4 GPa. As can be seen in Table I, a reasonable agreement is found between theory and experiment at 4.7 GPa. The calculated volume is overestimated by 3.7% with respect to the experimental value as a consequence of 3.4% and 2.6% bigger a and b axes. Although an overestimation of volume is typically associated with the use

of the GGA approximation, the percentage error is slightly larger than would normally be expected.

At pressures lower than 4 GPa there is an anomalous expansion of the cell. It can be related to an increase of symmetry of the monoclinic cell, which finally converges into an orthorhombic cell (S.G: *Cmcm*). The equilibrium cell volume of this new phase is 270 \AA^3 , with $a = 4.6406 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.3683 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 7.8963 \text{ \AA}$ and Ag (4b) (0.0,0.5,0.0), Ag (4c)(0.0,0.0520,0.25), S (4c)(0.0,0.689,0.25). As far as we know, this orthorhombic phase has not been detected previously. Since its equilibrium volume is clearly bigger than the ambient-pressure volume of the anticotunnite-type structure, it could correspond to a potential high-temperature phase of Ag_2S . In fact, this new theoretically predicted phase adopts a Ni_2In -type related structure (*Cmcm* is a subgroup of $P6_3/mmc$, space group of the Ni_2In compound), which is very common among the alkaline-metal sulfides. It basically consists of S-off-centered trigonal $[\text{Ag}_6]$ prisms similar to those present in the anti-cotunnite structure, but now forming straight chains along the c direction (see Fig. 2f). This structure will be discussed, together with the experimentally observed Ag_2S polymorphs, in the next section.

From the enthalpy-pressure curves, a transition to the Ag_2Se -type structure is found at 3.2 GPa (Fig. 8), with a volume change of 2.9 %. This is in good agreement with the experimental data, where the onset of the phase transition was observed at 5 GPa. Calculated structural data of the HP1-phase at 6.9 GPa are collected in Table I, to be compared with the experimental data. As described above, the coordination number of both the silver and the sulphur atoms do not change with increasing pressure. It remains constant each Ag1, Ag2 and S atoms having 5, 4 and 9 nearest neighbours, respectively. However, the relative movement of the different polyhedra led to a slight change in the environment of all the atoms and, consequently, to the phase transition. Furthermore, a numerical equation of state was fitted to our data giving the following parameters: $V_0=225.57 \text{ \AA}^3$, $B_0=74.27 \text{ GPa}$ and $B_0'=5.24$. By comparing these results with those experimentally obtained, we can see that the overestimation of volume by 3.9 % leads to a slightly smaller bulk modulus.

As regards the second phase transition, the theoretical simulations (Fig. 8) show the reappearance of the monoclinic structure at higher pressures (15.7 GPa). According to the *ab initio* calculations, this monoclinic phase has suffered some significant changes in its unit cell, such as a drastic decrease of the b axis and the β angle and a considerable increase of the c axis. This effect can be clearly noticed by comparing the lattice

parameters and atomic coordinates of the low pressure and HP2 structures in Table I. This behaviour was subsequently confirmed experimentally by means of the indexation and refinement of the XRD pattern at 16.5 GPa (see section 3.3). A more careful analysis of the structural parameters of this HP2 structure shows a close resemblance to a higher symmetry structure (S.G.: *Pnma*). At 16.7 GPa, $a = 5.7411 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 4.0443 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 8.0971 \text{ \AA}$, $\text{Ag}(4c) (0.0689, 0.75, 0.7807)$, $\text{Ag}(4c) (0.3435, 0.25, 0.9337)$, $\text{S}(4c) (0.3068, 0.25, 0.6104)$. As it can be observed from the relative enthalpy-pressure curves, the enthalpy of the *Pnma* structure equals that of the monoclinic structure at high pressures, confirming this fact. However, experimentally, a better fitting has been found using the monoclinic symmetry. The numerical equation of state parameters of the HP2 structure under the *Pnma* symmetry are: $V_0: 223.66 \text{ \AA}^3$, $B_0 = 57.04 \text{ GPa}$, $B_0' = 7.85$. Overall, the stability of the monoclinic phase is underestimated in comparison with the experimental results.

This understabilization is even more drastic when using the gradient level functionals PBEsol and AM05 and, particularly, the local density functional. According to these functionals, the HP1 phase is the most stable at very low pressures (<1GPa). Moreover, the cell volumes of all the phases are underestimated (Fig. 9) and the structural description in terms of the lattice parameters ratios departs from the experimental one (Fig. 10).

Phase diagrams more consistent with the experimental data can be obtained under the DFT+U approach. Although the *Cmcm* and *Pnma* phases are still present in the phase sequence, the range of stability of the monoclinic phase increases with growing U_{eff} value. Related to it, the HP1 structure is stable in a smaller pressure range. For example, when $U_{\text{eff}} = 6 \text{ eV}$ (Fig. 11) the orthorhombic phase is only stable from 3.7 GPa to 8.23 GPa, in comparison with the larger PBE pressure range (3.25-15.6 GPa). A reasonable structural description of the monoclinic structure is also obtained at pressures lower than 4 GPa (in particular, with $U_{\text{eff}} = 5-7 \text{ eV}$), as shown in Fig. 10. With $U_{\text{eff}} = 6 \text{ eV}$, the relative contractions of the lattice parameters a , b and c between ambient pressure and 4 GPa are 4.5, 4.8 and -0.4% in agreement with the experimental compressibility order (see Section 3.1). Additionally, there is a recovery of the monoclinic phase after the orthorhombic phase, in line with the experimental results. Concerning the HP1 phase, there is an increase of the cell volume with growing U_{eff} . Volume is already overestimated at the purely GGA level ($U_{\text{eff}} = 0$). Thus, introducing $U_{\text{eff}} > 0$ just makes the deviation from the experiment larger. However, it equalizes the

difference to experiment in all three vectors and the overall description of the cell improves, as the b/a and c/a ratios show (Fig. 12).

Previous authors³² have discussed the importance of including the non-bonded van der Waals interactions for silver chalcogenides. Preliminary calculations based on the GGA-D2 methodology of Grimme show the importance of including these contributions. They decrease the cell volumes approaching them to the experimental values. However, calculations at very low volumes tend to converge into excited states characterized by partial occupancies. Also, the description in terms of the lattice parameters ratios is worse than that obtained under the GGA+U methodology. It can be attributed to the parameters set of the GGA-D2 approach. The use of atomic-based parameters puts large dispersion coefficients on the Ag atoms and small forces on the S atoms. This results in too strong (weak) interactions between Ag (S) atoms.

3.5 Structural considerations

According to our high-pressure experimental (theoretical) study, the structural sequence of Ag_2S with increasing pressure is: ($Cmcm$) – anti- PbCl_2 -type, LP, $P2_1/n$ – Ag_2Se -type, HP1, $P2_12_12_1$ – anti- PbCl_2 -type, HP2, $P2_1/n$ – (anti- PbCl_2 -type, $Pnma$). Analysing the atomic rearrangements, it can be noticed that: (i) The theoretically predicted phase transition between the $Cmcm$ and the anticotunnite monoclinic structure seems to occur in the opposite direction to those observed in alkaline-metal sulfides under compression, where the anti- PbCl_2 -type structure transforms into the Ni_2In -type structure. However, the off-centring of the S atoms in the $[\text{Ag}_6]$ prisms of the $Cmcm$ phase (see Fig. 2f) would lead to a five-fold coordination of the S atoms, which would increase to 9, in the case of the $P2_1/n$ anticotunnite-type phase. Note that the ideal Ni_2In structure has a CN (S) =11. This distinguishing structural behaviour is likely related to the high electronegativity value of silver, compared to those of alkaline metals. Moreover, the relative stability of the anticotunnite- and the Ni_2In -type structures in the hypothetical high-pressure structural sequence of the A_2X compounds seems to vary from one compound to another³³, i.e. both structures are very close in energy. (ii) The first experimentally observed phase transition LP – HP1 in Ag_2S follows the well-known trend that the high-pressure structures of lighter elements (S in Ag_2S) adopt the structures of their parent heavier elements going down a column in the periodic table (Se in Ag_2Se). (iii) Upon further compression, the Ag_2Se -type structure, with tilted

chains of [Ag₆] prisms, return to the anti-cotunnite structure but now in a much more regular conformation, eventually adopting an orthorhombic space group in the theoretical calculations.

It is also interesting to compare the different Ag₂S polymorphs with the cation subarrays of their corresponding oxides. The Ag₂S subarray of Ag₂SO₃ (S.G. *P2₁/c*)³⁴ also adopts an anticotunnite-type structure, as in Ag₂S itself at room conditions. In this case, [Ag₆] prisms have expanded due to the presence of three O atoms per formula unit and form slightly warped chains. This case of structural similarity is in good agreement with numerous other examples of structural correspondence between alloys and the cation arrays in their oxides³⁵⁻³⁸. Ag₂SO₄, on the other hand, adopts a thenardite-type (S.G. *Fddd*) structure³⁹, whose cation subarray does not correspond to any of the high-pressure polymorphs of the silver sulphide. The cation arrangement in this oxide is similar to that of the TiSi₂ alloy. This structure was however predicted for Rb₂S at about 18 GPa⁴⁰ and has been considered as the intermediate step in the Ni₂In – Cu₂Al transition in the high-pressure sequence of the A₂X compounds³³. In other words, the structure of the cation subarray of Ag₂SO₄ could be a potential structure for Ag₂S at still higher pressures.

3.5 Conclusions

The high-pressure structural stability of acanthite Ag₂S has been studied by means of X-ray diffraction experiments as well as by *ab initio* calculations. From our experimental data, we have determined that two different high-pressure phase transitions take place. At 5 GPa, the initial anti-PbCl₂-type monoclinic structure (S.G. *P2₁/n*) transforms into an orthorhombic Ag₂Se-type structure (S.G. *P2₁2₁2₁*), which is a strong distortion of the initial phase. The volume collapse at the transition is about 1.3 %. In this structure, the chains of stuffed trigonal [SAg₆] prisms are not running parallel to each other anymore, but they are tilted with respect the adjacent ones. The compression of the initial *P2₁/n* structure is rather anisotropic and the experimental values of the bulk modulus and its first derivative with pressure are $B_0 = 38(2)$ GPa and $B'_0 = 12(2)$. The characteristic parameters of the *P2₁2₁2₁* HP1 structure obtained by fixing B'_0 to 5.2 are $V_0 = 217.2(2)$ Å³ and $B_0 = 84(2)$ GPa (theory: $V_0 = 225.57(3)$ Å³, $B_0 = 74.27(7)$ GPa, and $B'_0 = 5.24(1)$).

We have also found that compression induces a second phase transition at 10.5 GPa to a $P2_1/n$ phase which resembles the room-conditions structure. This HP2 monoclinic phase presents some significant changes in its unit cell with respect to the initial one, such as a drastic decrease of the b axis and the β angle and a considerable increase of the c axis. It is noteworthy that the initial monoclinic phase is fully recovered after decompression and that intermediate orthorhombic HP1 structure was not observed in downstroke. The sample seems to recover the unit cell parameters of the initial phase by means of a stepwise transformation from the also monoclinic HP2 structure.

Ab initio calculations confirm the experimental high-pressure sequence LP-HP1-HP2. Some deficiencies are found using standard DFT for modelling the electronic structure, but the GGA+U approach, with $U_{\text{eff}}=4-6$ eV is seen to perform better. A good agreement with experiment for transition pressures, lattice parameters and their variation with pressure is found. Two new phases arise from the simulations. A *Cmcm* structure is predicted to be stable at ambient conditions. On the other hand, HP2 is predicted to transform to a *Pnma* structure at high-pressures. The plausibility of it should be confirmed experimentally. In summary, we have presented a detailed and consistent experimental and theoretical picture of the high-pressure behaviour of Ag_2S .

3.6 Acknowledgments

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Table I.- Experimental and calculated PBE lattice parameters, volumes and fractional coordinates of Ag₂S in the low-pressure (LP) acanthite phase (anti-PbCl₂-type structure), in the first pressure-induced phase HP1 (Ag₂Se-type structure), and in the second pressure-induced phase HP2.

	LP phase		HP1 phase		HP2 phase	
	Experiment 4.7 GPa	Theory 4.7 GPa	Experiment 6.9 GPa	Theory 6.9 GPa	Experiment 16.5 GPa	Theory 16.5 GPa
Space Group	<i>P2₁/n</i> (14)	<i>P2₁/n</i>	<i>P2₁2₁2₁</i> (19)	<i>P2₁2₁2₁</i>	<i>P2₁/n</i> (14)	<i>P2₁/n</i>
a (Å)	4.1032(4)	4.2329	6.7249(12)	6.7791	4.0939(12)	4.1277
b (Å)	6.6391(6)	6.8078	4.1479(12)	4.3259	5.754(2)	5.7278
c (Å)	7.8183(7)	7.7259	7.2945(11)	7.1154	7.9747(11)	8.0343
β	99.480(5)	102.45	-	-	93.87(2)	94.810
Volume (Å³)	210.07(7)	217.4	203.4(2)	208.7	187.4(2)	189.3
x_{Ag1}	0.7419(9)	0.7634	0.0285(7)	0.0234	0.7366(18)	0.7331
y_{Ag1}	0.0277(5)	0.0214	0.2304(12)	0.241	0.0401(14)	0.0596
z_{Ag1}	0.3271(4)	0.3313	0.4081(15)	0.392	0.2928(8)	0.2843
x_{Ag2}	0.2476(8)	0.2471	0.1274(6)	0.1371	0.2573(18)	0.2545
y_{Ag2}	0.3440(5)	0.3452	0.4074(19)	0.401	0.2905(16)	0.3362
z_{Ag2}	0.4427(4)	0.4548	0.8210(6)	0.7886	0.4298(9)	0.4373
x_S	0.324(2)	0.3396	0.239(5)	0.2539	0.216(4)	0.2825
y_S	0.2608(13)	0.2426	0.176(4)	0.1313	0.259(5)	0.3013
z_S	0.1365(12)	0.1501	0.079(4)	0.0897	0.113(3)	0.1133

Figure Captions

Figure 1.- Selected x-ray powder diffraction patterns of Ag₂S. (a) Experiment 1, Xcalibur diffractometer, $\lambda(\text{Mo}) = \lambda_{\alpha_1} (0.7093 \text{ \AA}) + \lambda_{\alpha_2} (0.7136 \text{ \AA})$, using a mixture 4:1 methanol:ethanol as pressure-transmitting medium. Backgrounds subtracted. The XRD patterns at 5.4 GPa and 11.6 GPa clearly show the phase transitions to the HP1 and HP2 phases, respectively. The upper pattern was taken at room conditions after the decompression process and shows the reversibility of the transitions. (b) Experiment 2, Diamond Light Source, $\lambda = 0.4246 \text{ \AA}$, using a mixture 16:3:1 methanol:ethanol:water as pressure-transmitting medium. Backgrounds subtracted. The XRD patterns between 5.6 and 10.5 GPa show a coexistence of the initial LP phase and the HP1 phase (compare, for instance, the pattern at 8 GPa in this picture to that of 7.9 GPa in Fig. 1a, corresponding strictly to the HP1 phase).

Figure 2.- (a) Anticotunnite-type structure of the low-pressure $P2_1/n$ phase of Ag₂S at 3 GPa. (b) Projection of this LP phase along the b axis, showing that adjacent chains of prisms are shifted $1/2a$ and are parallel. (c) Ag₂Se-type structure of the HP1 $P2_12_12_1$ phase of Ag₂S at 6.9 GPa. (d) Projection of this HP1 phase along the a axis, showing that adjacent chains of prisms are shifted $1/2b$ and are tilted with respect to each other. (e) Anticotunnite-type structure of the HP2 $P2_1/n$ phase of Ag₂S at 16.5 GPa. (f) Projection along the a axis of the theoretically predicted $Cmcm$ phase for Ag₂S at low pressures.

Figure 3.- Observed, calculated, and difference x-ray diffraction profiles for the LP phase of Ag₂S at 3.2 GPa. Vertical markers indicate Bragg reflections of the initial $P2_1/n$ monoclinic structure.

Figure 4.- Pressure dependence of the unit-cell volume for the LP (squares), HP1 (circles) and HP2 (triangles) phases. Xcalibur (Experiment 1) and Diamond (Experiment 2) experimental data are represented by solid and empty symbols, respectively. Dashed lines correspond to the 3rd-order Birch-Murnaghan EOSs of the different phases (in the case of HP2 phase, only a linear fitting was done).

Figure 5.- Evolution of the lattice parameters of the low-pressure (a) and the HP1 (b) phases of Ag_2S with pressure according to our experimental (Xcalibur: solid symbols; Diamond: empty symbols) and ab initio PBE data (dashed lines). The a , b and c axes are represented by squares, circles and triangles, respectively. The β angle of the LP phase is represented by stars (Fig. 5a). Solid lines correspond to second-order polynomial (a) and linear (b) fittings to our experimental data. As can be seen, the contraction of the lattice parameters of both phases is rather anisotropic.

Figure 6.- Observed, calculated and difference X-ray diffraction profiles of orthorhombic $P2_12_12_1$ phase of Ag_2S at 6.9 GPa (HP1 phase). Vertical markers indicate Bragg reflections.

Figure 7.- Observed, calculated, and difference x-ray diffraction profiles for the HP2 phase of Ag_2S at 16.5 GPa. Vertical markers indicate Bragg reflections of the high-pressure $P2_1/n$ monoclinic structure.

Figure 8.- Enthalpy differences, relative the the low-pressure structure (LP), as a function of pressure for the $Cmcm$, HP1 and $Pnma$ structures of Ag_2S . Calculations were performed at the PBE level.

Figure 9.- Pressure dependence of the unit-cell volume for the three phases of Ag_2S . Xcalibur (Experiment 1) and Diamond (Experiment 2) experimental data are represented by solid and empty symbols, respectively. Squares, circles and triangles correspond to the LP, HP1 and HP2 phases. Calculated data using the GGA functionals: PBE, PBEsol, AM05, the GGA+U approach, with U values of 7, 6, 5, 4 eV and the conventional LDA functional are represented by linespoints. Dashed lines indicate the phase boundaries. The region between 10.5 and 14 GPa is the coexistence region of the HP1 and HP2 phases.

Figure 10.- Lattice parameters ratios b/a and c/a as a function of pressure for the low pressure phase (LP). Experimental data are represented by solid (Experiment 1, Xcalibur) and empty (Experiment 2, Diamond) squares. Calculated data using the GGA functional: PBEsol, AM05, the GGA+U approach, with U values of 7,6,5 eV and the conventional LDA functional are represented by linespoints.

Figure 11.- Enthalpy differences, relative the the low-pressure structure (LP), as a function of pressure for the *Cmcm*, HP1 and *Pnma* structures of Ag₂S. Calculations were performed at the GGA+U level, with U=6eV.

Figure 12.- Lattice parameters ratios b/a and c/a as a function of pressure for the HP1 phase. Experimental data are represented by solid (Experiment 1, Excalibur) and empty (Experiment 2, Diamond) squares. Calculated data using the GGA functional: PBE, PBEsol, AM05, the GGA+U approach, with U values of 6, 5, 4 eV and the conventional LDA functional are represented by linespoints.

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Figure 1

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Figure 3

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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

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Figure 10

Figure 11